

1 **Eastern Mediterranean climate change deduced from the Soreq**
2 **Cave fluid inclusion stable isotopes and carbonate clumped**
3 **isotopes record of the last 160 ka.**

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Highlights

1. Clumped isotope thermometry and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ enable creation of cave water $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ record.
2. $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ values derived from clumped isotopes agree with fluid inclusion measurements.
3. Temperatures vary from interglacial values of 20-22°C to 11-12°C in glacial maxima.
4. d-excess values vary between GMWL and EMMWL in cold and warm periods, respectively.
5. Temperature rise controls $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ change during the initiation of Terminations.

31 **Abstract**

32 A fundamental issue in the interpretation of speleothem calcite $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ records is the correct
33 partitioning of the effects of temperature and water $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ variation. This study explores the
34 paleo-environmental evolution of the Eastern Mediterranean Sea (EMS) region using Soreq
35 Cave speleothems in the last 160 ka, a period covering glacial MIS6 to the present, through
36 the independent determinations of temperatures via carbonate clumped isotopes (Δ_{47}) and
37 fluid inclusion $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$, $\delta\text{D}_{\text{w}}$ and d-excess values of cave water entrapped in the speleothems.
38 The observed general agreement between the trends in water $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ composition directly
39 measured from fluid inclusions and calculated from Δ_{47} temperatures and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ support the
40 robustness of the data. Δ_{47} temperatures, derived using a revised thermometer calibration that
41 includes recent modifications in ^{17}O correction, vary from high values of 20-22°C during
42 interglacial periods to low values of 11-12°C in cold glacial and stadial periods.
43 Temperatures of 19-22°C are observed during the time of deposition in the Eastern
44 Mediterranean Sea of sapropel S5 during the last interglacial MIS5e period and sapropel S1
45 in the early Holocene, immediately following Terminations II and I, respectively. The Soreq
46 Cave Δ_{47} temperatures generally agree with previously estimated EM sea surface
47 temperatures, in support of the absence of a significant land-sea temperature gradient. Cave
48 water $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ values show large variations (from ~ -3 to -7.5‰), with high glacial and low
49 interglacial values. These variations are largely explained by changes in Mediterranean Sea
50 water composition due to glacial ice melting and freshwater input during sapropel periods,
51 combined with the effect of rainfall amounts during interglacial periods. An analysis of
52 relative timing shows that temperature rise dominates hydrological changes in the initial
53 stages of Termination events. Fluid inclusion d-excess values show clear variations between
54 values similar to the Global Meteoric Water Line in cold periods and the local Eastern
55 Mediterranean Meteoric Water Line in warm periods.

56

57 Keywords: Glacial-Interglacial, Paleoclimatology, Speleothems, Eastern Mediterranean,
58 Soreq Cave, Fluid inclusions, Carbonate clumped isotopes, stable isotopes,
59 paleotemperatures, Terminations II and I.

60

61 **1. Introduction**

62 Unravelling the complex carbonate $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ records of cave speleothems is complicated by
63 the need to separate the contribution of temperature change from that of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ in the cave
64 water from which the speleothem grew. The continuous record of climate change given by
65 the speleothems of Soreq Cave (Israel), located in the Eastern Mediterranean (EM) region,
66 provide an excellent foundation for addressing the important question of temperature versus
67 hydrology in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ record. Previous studies of modern and past speleothem deposits
68 using clumped isotope (Δ_{47}) thermometry and fluid inclusion D/H studies have indeed shown
69 that Soreq Cave records a history of glacial-interglacial temperature change and variations in
70 the EMMWL $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ - δD relationship (Matthews et al., 2000; McGarry et al., 2004; Affek et al.,
71 2008; Affek et al., 2014).

72 Soreq Cave speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ values are accurately dated continuous archives of
73 Glacial-Interglacial climate changes in semi-arid Mediterranean climate during the last 180
74 ka (Fig.1) (Bar-Matthews et al., 2003; Grant et al., 2012; 2016). The well-defined negative
75 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ peaks (Fig. 1) coincide with glacial terminations TII and TI and with the ~23ky
76 Milankovitch precession cycle maxima during which organic carbon-rich sapropel deposits
77 are present in the Eastern Mediterranean Sea (EMS) (Bar-Matthews et al., 2000; de Lange et
78 al., 2008; Almogi-Labin et al., 2009). Specific features of importance in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record
79 include the stepwise development of a strong negative $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ peak starting during late glacial
80 Marine Isotope Stage 6 (MIS6) and peaking during the previous interglacial MIS5e (up to -

81 9‰ during MIS5e; Fig. 1) and a similar peak during the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM, 19
82 ka) to Holocene transition. In contrast, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ maxima are typical of the cold and dry glacial
83 conditions, with values up to -2‰. During the Last Glacial period from 120 to 20 ka, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$
84 progressively increases, reflecting the gradual progression from the last interglacial period
85 MIS5e towards the LGM. Thus, the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ variations of the Soreq Cave record are typically
86 taken to represent paleoclimate conditions varying from warm and humid peak interglacial
87 periods to cold and arid conditions during glacial maxima (e.g., [Bar-Matthews et al., 1997](#);
88 [Bar-Matthews et al., 2003](#); [Bar-Matthews et al., 2019](#)). Partitioning the variations in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$
89 into the contributions of temperature and cave water $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ requires independent knowledge
90 of one or both these parameters. Temperature variations are an obvious control on Glacial-
91 Interglacial changes. In contrast, variations in rainfall $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ and how they are reflected in
92 cave drip water are complex, and in the EM region they reflect multiple processes.
93 Partitioning the effects of temperature and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ variation is therefore a key to a full
94 understanding of cave $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ records. Here, we combine carbonate clumped isotope
95 thermometry with measurements of $\delta\text{D}_{\text{w}}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ in fluid inclusions to independently
96 determine the temperature-water evolution of Soreq Cave over the last 160 ka. Carbonate
97 clumped isotopes refer to measurements of the relative abundance of $^{13}\text{C}-^{18}\text{O}$ bonds within
98 the carbonate lattice. It is measured in CO_2 extracted from CaCO_3 , using the parameter Δ_{47} ,
99 that is composed of mostly $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}^{16}\text{O}$ (with minor contributions from $^{13}\text{C}^{17}\text{O}^{17}\text{O}$ and
100 $^{12}\text{C}^{17}\text{O}^{18}\text{O}$), whose abundance is reported relative to CO_2 in which the heavy isotopes are
101 randomly distributed among all isotopologues. For a carbonate that forms at high
102 temperatures the heavy, rare, isotopes tend to be randomly distributed among the chemical
103 bonds within the lattice, resulting in low Δ_{47} values ([Eiler, 2007](#); [Affek, 2012](#)). At low
104 temperatures, there is a preference for the two heavy isotopes to bind together, resulting in
105 high Δ_{47} values (e.g., [Ghosh et al., 2006](#)). As such, the measurement of Δ_{47} in CO_2 extracted

106 from a carbonate archive serves as a geochemical thermometer, reflecting the temperature in
107 which the carbonate mineral grew. Thus, clumped isotope thermometry also allows to
108 calculate cave water $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ using the carbonate-water oxygen isotope thermometer

109 Whereas both carbonate clumped and oxygen isotope thermometers are based on
110 thermodynamic behavior, it has been shown that in speleothems these isotopic tracers are
111 affected by dis-equilibrium (e.g., [Affek et al., 2008, 2014](#); [Daëron et al., 2011](#); [Kluge et al.,](#)
112 [2014](#); [Guo and Zhou, 2019](#)). These effects are related to kinetic isotope effects associated
113 with CO_2 degassing from cave drip water, followed by fast CaCO_3 precipitation, leading to
114 an increase in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and a decrease in Δ_{47} . Although this phenomenon is not fully understood,
115 it can be accounted for in speleothem thermometry using a combination of laboratory
116 experiments and modern cave characterization (e.g., in Soreq Cave: [Affek and Zaarur, 2014](#);
117 [Affek et al., 2014](#)).

118 Direct determination of cave water $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ and δD_w is possible through Fluid Inclusion
119 (FI) analysis. Fluid inclusions are small amounts of water that were trapped within the
120 speleothem carbonate while it was growing. The water inclusions, that can be extracted and
121 analyzed for $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ and δD_w , thus potentially reflect cave water isotopic composition at the
122 time of deposition of the speleothem layer. Studies using mechanical crushing and continuous
123 flow IRMS or Cavity Ring Down Spectroscopy (CRDS) show this assumption to be valid in
124 a wide variety of samples ([Vonhof et al., 2006](#); [Van Breukelen et al., 2008](#); [Dublyansky and](#)
125 [Spötl., 2009](#); [Zhang et al., 2008](#); [Griffiths et al., 2010](#); [Labuhn et al., 2015](#); [Meckler et al.,](#)
126 [2015](#); [Affolter et al., 2014., 2019](#); [de Graaf et al., 2020](#)). Nevertheless, these studies have
127 been mostly performed on samples from regions of high amounts of rainfall, and the extent to
128 which this assumption applies to semi-arid environments, such as the EM where rainfall is
129 seasonal, has not yet been fully substantiated.

130 In this study, we observe a link between FI $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ values and water yields and the
131 growth habit of the calcite crystals. Previous studies (Ayalon et al. (1999); Bar-Matthews et
132 al. (1997) defined three main types of petrographic textures in Soreq speleothems: 1) large
133 elongated calcite crystals (several hundred μm or more) with a preferred orientation parallel
134 to the c-axis (e.g., Figs. 1D, E in Ayalon et al., 1999). This petrographic type represents slow
135 deposition in continuous water drip conditions that allowed elongated crystals to develop, and
136 is found in speleothem calcite from both glacial and interglacial periods. 2) Fine grained (10-
137 $50\mu\text{m}$) equant to anhedral randomly orientated crystals. This texture reflects rapid crystal
138 growth at high water drip rates, and are common in peak interglacial conditions, particularly
139 periods of enhanced rainfall resulting in fast dripping. This growth pattern coincides with ^{18}O
140 depletion associated with the warm interglacial/interstadial intervals that form the climatic
141 backdrop of sapropel deposition in the Eastern Mediterranean Sea. 3) Elongated crystals that
142 are partially overgrown by fine-grained crystals (e.g., Fig. 1H in Ayalon et al., 1999), with
143 the elongated type being dominant. Such alternation represents periods of climate oscillation
144 during the deglaciation events so that these textures are always associated with the
145 Terminations.

146 This paper presents a new record of Δ_{47} -based temperatures and fluid inclusion water
147 isotope composition from Soreq Cave, covering two periods of glacial-interglacial change.
148 The paper primarily addresses the interactions between temperature and water isotopic
149 composition over time that produce the observed Soreq $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{cc}$ record of the last 160 ka. The
150 particular focus is on periods of significant change in the EM region resulting from global
151 warming and sea level changes during Terminations II and I, and the potential shifts of
152 temperatures as well as sea and rain water $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ during peak interglacial periods, coincident
153 with formation of sapropels S5 and S1 in the EMS.

154

155 **2. Methodology**

156 2.1. Speleothem sampling

157 A total of 48 samples were analyzed for Δ_{47} and for FI δD and $\delta^{18}O_w$. Sampling was
158 performed by circular saw sectioning of accurately dated speleothem slices at the Geological
159 Survey of Israel (GSI). The sample size was dictated by the need to provide 0.6 – 0.8g size
160 pieces for fluid inclusion (FI) analysis and generally consisted of small sectioned cubes
161 approximately 0.5 cm thick weighing several grams, which were then mechanically broken
162 up to provide suitable sized chips for FI measurements. One or two mm sized fragments were
163 used for FI extraction as described below and a small fragment was used for Δ_{47} analysis. The
164 mean ages of the sectioned speleothem samples together with their error range are given in
165 Table 1. The size of the sample cube defines the mean and uncertainty of the U-Th age
166 (typical approximate error of ± 0.2 ka for the younger samples and ± 2 ka for the older
167 samples). Thus, FI and Δ_{47} are measured on different pieces of sample from the same age
168 window. Similarly, mean $\delta^{18}O_{cc}$ values and their error range (estimated at $\pm 0.5\%$ for the age
169 range of the sample cubes) reflect variability that is averaged out in the sample cube. This is
170 not the analytical error but the result of the variability observed in a relatively large time
171 window that is averaged. $\delta^{18}O_{cc}$ values (Table 1) are taken from data in previous high
172 resolution studies performed at the Geological Survey of Israel (GSI). The isotope stage and
173 time period to which the samples belong and the petrographic types, categorized according to
174 the classification given in the introduction, are detailed in Supplementary Information Table
175 S1.

176

177 2.2. Δ_{47} analytical method

178 Carbonate clumped isotopes measurements were performed in Yale University,
179 following the method described previously (e.g., [Affek et al., 2014](#)). Briefly, $CaCO_3$ (3-4 mg)

180 was digested overnight by 103% H₃PO₄ at 25°C. The CO₂ extracted from the carbonate
181 sample was purified cryogenically and by passing through a GC column (Supelco Q-Plot,
182 30m long 0.53 mm ID, at -20°C). Samples were measured in at least triplicates. The purified
183 CO₂ was analyzed for the abundance of masses 44-49, from which the values of δ¹³C, δ¹⁸O
184 and Δ₄₇ were calculated, using a Thermo MAT-253 mass spectrometer. Each measurement
185 consisted of 90 cycles of sample-reference comparisons, with a signal integration time of
186 8sec. Analytical uncertainty is reported as the standard error of the mean. The typical
187 standard deviation of the Soreq Cave samples reported here is 0.017‰, which results in
188 0.010‰ standard error for triplicate analyses.

189 Values of Δ₄₇ are reported relative to a reference frame that is based on “heated CO₂”
190 in which the heavy isotopes are randomly distributed among all isotopologues, together with
191 CO₂ equilibrated with water at low temperatures, in which the Δ₄₇ value is defined by
192 theoretical calculations (following the approach of [Dennis et al., 2011](#)). Recently, a reference
193 frame that is based on a set of inter-laboratory CaCO₃ standards has been suggested
194 ([Bernasconi et al., 2021](#)), which is based on the same principles of heated and equilibrated
195 CO₂, by bracketing the range of δ¹³C and δ¹⁸O as well as the range of Δ₄₇ of typical samples.
196 The data presented in this study was measured prior to the introduction of these standards and
197 is therefore standardized by the CO₂-based reference frame, as described in the
198 supplementary material of [Zaarur et al. \(2016\)](#).

199 Values of Δ₄₇ were calculated with the originally used isotopic parameters ([Affek and](#)
200 [Eiler, 2006](#); [Huntington et al., 2009](#)), in which the presence of ¹⁷O containing CO₂
201 isotopologues was accounted for using values derived from [Gonfiantini et al. \(1995\)](#), similar
202 to those used in the mass spectrometer software ([Santrock et al., 1985](#)). Data was then recast
203 into a reference frame based on CO₂ equilibrated at various temperatures (termed absolute
204 reference frame or CDES, following [Dennis et al., 2011](#)) using the procedure described in

205 [Zaarur et al. \(2016\)](#); see their Supplementary Information for details). Recently, however, it
206 was recognized that these parameters may result in a significant error in Δ_{47} especially for
207 samples in which $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ are significantly different from the mass spectrometer
208 reference gas ([Daëron et al., 2016](#)). Instead, the recommended ^{17}O parameters are those of
209 [Brand et al. \(2010\)](#). Here, we report the Δ_{47} data using both parameter sets (termed Brand and
210 Gonfiantini parameters, respectively), with the data being recalculated into the Brand
211 parameters using the Excel template provided by [Daëron et al. \(2016\)](#).

212 For that, we recalculate all sample data, together with data of equilibrated CO_2 and
213 laboratory standards used for recasting the data into the absolute reference frame (see details
214 in the Supplementary Information of [Dawson et al., 2020](#)). We also recalculate the data of
215 $\Delta_{47}\text{-T}$ calibration material ([Zaarur et al., 2013](#), [Affek and Zaarur, 2014](#)). Note that the
216 calculation of Δ_{47} assumes that all samples have an $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ value of zero. [Bergel et al. \(2020\)](#)
217 showed, however, $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of about $-0.150 \pm 0.020\%$ in freshwater mollusks in Israel.
218 Assuming that this is the typical value for freshwater carbonates, so that our samples have a
219 similar $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$, results in an offset of $0.005 \pm 0.001\%$ in Δ_{47} . This offset is consistent with
220 recent estimates of the effect on Δ_{47} of variable $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in CO_2 standards ([Saenger et al.,](#)
221 [2021](#)). As this offset is almost constant for all our samples it does not affect the temperatures
222 derived from Δ_{47} and we therefore neglect it.

223

224 2.3. Fluid Inclusion methods

225 Fluid inclusion δD_w and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ values, from which d-excess was calculated, were
226 obtained at the Vrije Universiteit (Amsterdam). Whereas the previous studies of Matthews et
227 al. (2000) and McGarry et al. (2004) used thermal decrepitation to determine FI δD_w , the
228 analytical method in this study used a He flow crushing – continuous flow isotope ratio mass
229 spectrometer (CFIRMS) system (Vonhof et al., 2006; van Breukelen et al., 2008; Labuhn et

230 al., 2015). Similar crushing-based methods were developed in other laboratories (e.g.,
231 [Demény and Siklosy, 2008](#); [Dublyansky and Spötl, 2009](#)) and were shown to be very
232 effective in FI δD_w and $\delta^{18}O_w$ analysis. A recent comparison of CFIRMS-based crusher
233 systems with infrared spectroscopy based systems confirms the good reproducibility of data
234 between these analytical platforms ([de Graaf et al., 2020](#)). Samples consisted of 1 or 2 chips
235 weighing in total 0.6 to 0.8g. Sample crushing was done using an automated crusher heated at
236 120°C to prevent water from being adsorbed on the powder created during crushing. Prior to
237 crushing, samples were also pre-heated at 120°C in a helium stream, to remove water
238 adsorbed on the surface of the sample ([Dennis et al, 2001](#); [Vonhof et al., 2006](#)). Water
239 released during crushing (or by injection of 0.2 μ l of a water standard into the crushing
240 chamber; see below) was trapped in a spiral coil immersed in an ethyl alcohol – liquid N₂
241 bath at < -90°C over a period of 4 minutes, and then rapidly heated and released in a helium
242 stream into a Thermo-Finnigan TC-EA pyrolysis furnace where water was reduced to H₂ and
243 CO for δD and $\delta^{18}O$ mass spectrometric measurement, respectively ([Vonhof et al., 2006](#); [van](#)
244 [Breukelen et al., 2008](#); [Labuhn et al., 2015](#)). These gases were then carried into a continuous
245 flow mass spectrometer (Thermo, Delta+) for isotopic analysis. The mass spectrometer was
246 calibrated using an in-house water standard of known isotopic composition. A typical run
247 sequence would consist of three injections of 0.2 μ l of the laboratory water standard followed
248 by the water extracted from the crushed sample. The water yield in μ l/g, which is a function
249 of the sample water content and extraction yield, was then calculated by comparing the
250 sample's CO peak area with that of the water standard. The sample analysis was bracketed by
251 running the water standard at amounts above and below the sample yield. The δD and $\delta^{18}O$
252 values of a sample were then derived by comparison to the relevant peak size in the
253 bracketing water standards.

254 Corrections for mass spectrometer linearity were made by comparing the measured
255 isotopic values of three laboratory standards to their known values (DNS3 -9.95 ‰, -1.43‰;
256 ALW13 -59.53‰, -8.37‰; KEILA -158.4‰, -21.2‰ for δD and $\delta^{18}O$, respectively). The
257 correction factors (multiplicative) for isotopic memory, estimated from the isotopic
258 composition shifts during consecutive injections of DNS3 and KEILA standard waters, were
259 1.018 for δD_w and 1.010 for $\delta^{18}O_w$. Overall, 2 standard errors estimated on the basis of
260 repeated analyses of 0.1 μl DNS3 are $\pm 3.3\%$ for δD_w and $\pm 0.43\%$ for $\delta^{18}O_w$. Duplicate
261 analyses that were made on a number of samples fall within or close to these errors (Table 1).

262 Water yields were highly variable, varying from $< 0.05 \mu l/g$ to $\sim 0.5 \mu l/g$ (Table 1).
263 Very low yield samples are considered problematic because small amounts of nitrogen (from
264 air) in the crusher may be converted in the TC/EA to NO whose primary isotopic mass
265 $^{14}N^{16}O$ overlaps with the $^{12}C^{18}O$ peak, and therefore may yield anomalously high $\delta^{18}O_w$
266 values. Consequently, all samples with yields less than $0.04 \mu l/g$ were not measured for their
267 isotopic composition, though their FI yield is included in the database (Table 1). The use of
268 larger speleothem samples was not possible for such low yield cases because this resulted in
269 only marginal yield increase, as frequently the fine powder generated during crushing
270 blocked the capillaries carrying the gases from the crusher.

271

272 3. Results

273 Primary data used in this study are presented in Table 1. The complete data, including
274 errors and additional data mentioned in the text are presented in Table S1 of the
275 Supplementary Information.

276

277 3.1. Δ_{47} data

278 Δ_{47} values, calculated using the Brand parameters are given in Table 1. The mean
279 ages of the speleothem samples are given together with the error range defined by the
280 thickness of the sectioned cubes (see section 2.1 for sampling details). Similarly, mean
281 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ values and their error range ($\pm 0.5\text{‰}$) reflect the values that are the average of data
282 obtained in previous studies (at the GSI) for the age range covered by each sample cube.

283 The Δ_{47} data from Table 1 are plotted as a function of age in Fig. 2. The Δ_{47} values
284 range from 0.67 to 0.73 with the highest values (>0.71) observed during cold glacial/stadial
285 periods MIS6, MIS4, parts of MIS3, and MIS2. In contrast, lower Δ_{47} values (<0.70) occur in
286 the major interglacial periods (Holocene and MIS5e). Generally, the 115-20 ka period is
287 characterized by a gradual, but variable rise in Δ_{47} , with values generally above 0.70 (the
288 lowest value in this period is 0.695). Given, the inverse relationship between Δ_{47} and
289 temperature (Ghosh et al., 2006; Affek and Zaarur, 2014), this gradually increasing trend of
290 Δ_{47} values reflects decreasing temperatures as will be discussed in detail in section 4.1.

291

292 3.1.1. Δ_{47} data using Gonfiantini versus Brand parameters

293 For all Soreq samples (excluding two samples, SO-15-A and SO-15-B, described
294 below) the Δ_{47} value calculated using the Brand parameters is lower by $0.005\pm 0.004\text{‰}$ than
295 that calculated using the Gonfiantini parameters (Table S1). The fast drip modern Soreq
296 stalagmites that are used to anchor the Δ_{47} -T calibration for Soreq Cave (Affek et al., 2014)
297 are lower using the Brand parameters by $0.008\pm 0.001\text{‰}$. As such, the choice of parameters
298 does not significantly affect the temporal trend of temperatures observed in Soreq cave. The
299 difference between the two sets of parameters may vary with the type of standards used and
300 is expected to correlate (with opposing trends) with both $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (Daëron et al., 2016);
301 it is therefore expected to vary with the difference between $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$. In Soreq samples

302 this difference ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ minus $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) has a narrow range ($-5\pm 2\text{‰}$), so that it is not surprising that
303 the difference between Gonfiantini and Brand parameters in these samples is approximately
304 constant.

305 A few samples (asterisks in Table 1) were measured in Caltech (as part of [Affek et al.,](#)
306 [2008](#)). For these samples the raw data needed to recalculate the data into the Brand
307 parameters is not available. As the difference between $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in these samples is
308 within the same range as the rest of Soreq Cave samples, we recast them in the Brand
309 parameters by subtracting the mean 0.005‰ offset.

310 In two samples, SO-15-A and SO-15-B, dated to 123 and 128 ka, respectively, the
311 difference between $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ is $+8$ and $+3\text{‰}$, respectively. This is very different from
312 the rest of the samples and indeed in these samples the Brand parameters result in Δ_{47} that is
313 lower than the Gonfiantini parameters by 0.021 and 0.016‰ (Table S1). These two samples
314 are the only cases in which the temperature derived from Δ_{47} significantly changes when
315 using the Brand versus Gonfiantini parameters.

316

317 3.1.2. Δ_{47} -T calibration in the Brand parameters

318 In order to calculate temperature from Δ_{47} , a choice has to be made with respect to the
319 most suitable Δ_{47} -T calibration. For modern and Holocene Soreq Cave samples we previously
320 examined two calibrations, based on laboratory precipitation experiments, one in the bulk of
321 the solution ([Zaarur et al., 2013](#)) and another in the solution surface ([Affek and Zaarur,](#)
322 [2014](#)). We then used the modern Soreq Cave fast drip stalagmite data to anchor the
323 calibration relevant to Soreq ([Affek et al., 2014](#)). In order to use a similar approach here (see
324 section 4.1 below for details) we have to recalculate also the data used in these calibrations
325 using the Brand parameters.

326 [Daëron et al. \(2016\)](#) suggested that the slope of the Δ_{47} -T relationship does not
327 significantly change when converting the data to the Brand parameters, but the intercept may
328 change significantly. Although a Brand version to the [Zaarur et al. \(2013\)](#) calibration has
329 been recalculated previously ([Daëron et al., 2016](#), [Evans et al., 2018](#), [Dawson et al., 2020](#)) we
330 calculate it here again, as some of the raw data that is available now was not available in
331 these previous studies, and in order to make sure that the calculations and standardizations
332 are done in exactly the same way as the Soreq Cave samples. The intercept of the Brand
333 parameters Δ_{47} -T bulk solution calibration ([Zaarur et al., 2013](#); denoted $Z13_{\text{Brand}}$) is higher by
334 0.038‰ than the respective line in the Gonfiantini parameters, resulting in a Δ_{47} -T
335 relationship:

$$336 \quad \Delta_{47}(Z13_{\text{Brand}}) = 0.0523 * 10^6 / T^2 + 0.1296.$$

337 Similar calculation for the surface precipitation data ([Affek and Zaarur, 2014](#); denoted
338 $AZ14_{\text{Brand}}$) results in only a small change, with the intercept in the Brand parameters lower by
339 0.001‰ than the respective Gonfiantini parameters line. The resulting Δ_{47} -T relationship is:

$$340 \quad \Delta_{47}(AZ14_{\text{Brand}}) = 0.0404 * 10^6 / T^2 + 0.2123.$$

341

342 3.2. Fluid inclusion stable isotope data

343 Measured FI $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ and δD_w values are given in Table 1 and plotted as a function of
344 age in Figs. 3a and 3b, respectively. $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ values span a range of $\sim 4.5\%$, between -2.5% and
345 -7% . The most significant shifts occur during the transitions from the glacial MIS6 to MIS5e
346 (Termination II; from -7 to -4%) and the LGM to the Holocene (Termination I; from -6.5 to $-$
347 2.5%). During the last Glacial period ($\sim 115 - 20$ ka) $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ values vary from -5% to -2.5%
348 but do not show a clearly defined trend of either decrease or increase. One glacial sample, at
349 45.3 ± 2 ka, gives notably high $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ and δD values of -1.2% and $+6\%$, respectively. A short-

350 lived cold and dry event at this time is also implied by the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ records (Fig. 1 and
351 [Bar-Matthews et al., 2019](#)).

352 The quality of FI data is potentially related to the water yield obtained in each sample.
353 Whereas isotopic data was not determined for samples with yield below 0.04 $\mu\text{l/g}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and
354 δD values were measured for samples that are somewhat larger (Table 1). It is also notable
355 that there is a general correlation between the petrographic habit of the calcite crystals and
356 the water yield (Table S1). Some of the samples that formed at peak interglacial/interstadial
357 conditions, contemporaneous with sapropel deposition in the EMS, had low yield (S1: 6.4 ka,
358 6.8 ka, 8.4 ka; S3: 86.0 ka; S4: 103.7 ka; S5: 125 ka). These samples comprise the low
359 porosity, fine grained crystal type identified by [Ayalon et al. \(1999\)](#). High yield is obtained in
360 samples from the Late Glacial MIS6, Termination II, Termination I, and the mid-Holocene
361 periods, where samples are dominated by the elongated habit of slow growing crystals. Low
362 yields in FI crushing methods were first noted by [Dennis et al. \(2001\)](#).

363 Generally, δD_w values vary between -30 and -10‰ and show less systematic variation
364 compared to $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$, even during major transition periods, such as during Terminations I and
365 II. The Global Meteoric Water Line (GMWL): $\delta\text{D}_w = 8 * \delta^{18}\text{O}_w + 10$ ([Craig, 1961](#)) has a
366 deuterium excess (d-excess = $\delta\text{D}_w - 8 * \delta^{18}\text{O}_w$) of 10‰. In contrast, the local Eastern
367 Mediterranean Meteoric water line (EMMWL) is characterized by a high d-excess value of
368 ~22‰ ([Gat and Carmi, 1987](#)), reflecting a local meteoric water line of present-day winter
369 rainfall. The higher local d-excess is the result of kinetic fractionations due to the large
370 relative humidity contrast between water vapor above the warm EMS surface and the cold-
371 dry cyclonic air streams moving off the European continent. A plot of δD_w versus $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ (Fig.
372 4) indicates that most data are either close to the EMMWL or between the EMMWL and
373 GMWL (as was already inferred by [Matthews et al., 2000](#) and [McGarry et al., 2004](#)). The
374 grey shaded area in Fig. 4 depicts the range of δD_w and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ values of present-day rainfall

375 above the Soreq Cave. Typically, the rainfall d-excess values vary between 20-30‰ with an
376 average value of 21.3 ± 3.1 ‰ (1 standard deviation) for the years 1995-2020. Many of the
377 fluid inclusion data overlap with this range, but a significant number of data points are lower,
378 close to the GMWL (Fig. 4). Samples that are close to the GMWL range are typically
379 associated with cold glacial periods, whereas interglacial period samples are closer to the
380 EMMWL.

381

382 **4. Discussion**

383 The discussion focusses on the contributions of temperature and sea surface water
384 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ change to the changes of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{cc}$ at glacial-interglacial transitions (e.g., Terminations II
385 (145-128 ka) and I (25-11 ka) in Fig. 1). The time series covered in this study includes two
386 glacial termination events at relatively high resolution, and low resolution data through the
387 last glacial. Additional features of the time series are the negative $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{cc}$ peaks in the
388 speleothem calcite record, immediately following the terminations, that correspond to
389 sapropel formation events in the EMS (Fig. 1). The formation of these organic carbon rich
390 sediments is related to slowdown in the Mediterranean thermohaline intermediate and deep
391 water formation (Rohling et al., 2015). Recent U-Mo isotope studies have validated the
392 slowdown in EMS deep water circulation rate during two major sapropel events covered in
393 this study, S5 and S1 (Andersen et al., 2018, 2020). This occurs through the creation of a low
394 density surface water layer due to enhanced influx of low $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ freshwater from the Nile
395 River and North African rivers (that are dry at present) during periods of African monsoon
396 maxima, together with increased rainfall from Atlantic westerlies in the Mediterranean
397 region, and post-glacial sea level rise (Rossignol-Strick, 1985; Rohling, 1994; Thomson et
398 al., 1999; Kallel et al., 2000; Emeis et al., 1998, 2000a,b, 2003; Scrivner et al., 2004; Bar-
399 Matthews et al., 2000; de Lange et al., 2008; Osborne et al., 2008; Bar-Matthews, 2014;

400 [Grant et al., 2016](#)). Sapropel formation periods are used as a time marker of peak insolation
401 conditions in this study and the speleothems deposited at this time will be referred to as
402 ‘sapropel period’ samples.

403

404 4.1 Clumped isotope temperatures

405 4.1.1. Choice of Δ_{47} -T calibration

406 The pioneering study of Δ_{47} in Soreq Cave ([Affek et al., 2008](#)) suggested that
407 stalagmites do not form at isotopic equilibrium, so that their $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ and Δ_{47} are offset to
408 higher and lower values, respectively. This results from degassing of CO_2 from the cave drip
409 water solution in which the stalagmite grows, that is not fully buffered by re-equilibration via
410 isotope exchange with water, due to the fast carbonate precipitation in the thin film of
411 solution. Since then, this phenomenon has been observed in multiple studies, either in cave
412 observations (e.g., [Daëron et al., 2011](#); [Wainer et al., 2010](#); [Kluge and Affek, 2012](#); [Kluge et](#)
413 [al., 2013](#) for Δ_{47}) or in laboratory experiments and modelling studies (e.g., [Day and](#)
414 [Henderson, 2011](#); [Dreybrodt and Scholz, 2011](#); [Watkins et al., 2013](#); [Hansen et al., 2019](#);
415 [Guo and Zhou 2019](#)). [Affek and Zaarur \(2014\)](#) attempted to characterize the relationship of
416 Δ_{47} with temperature in thin film condition, that may be relevant to speleothems, by
417 precipitating CaCO_3 rafts, floating at the surface of the $\text{Ca}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$ solutions from which they
418 form (hereafter denoted surface precipitation or AZ14). They found Δ_{47} values that are lower
419 than the standard (bulk solution) Δ_{47} -T calibration, consistent with cave observations. A
420 thorough investigation of modern and Holocene speleothems from Soreq Cave ([Affek et al.,](#)
421 [2014](#)) was interpreted to suggest that stalagmites forming in fast drip sites in the cave have
422 Δ_{47} values that are between the standard calibration and the surface precipitation Δ_{47} -T
423 relationship. Temperatures for Soreq samples were therefore calculated using a mid-point

424 calibration that was based on both sets of calibrations but was anchored to the modern-day
425 Soreq Cave temperature.

426 In these studies, Δ_{47} values were determined using the Gonfiantini parameters in
427 accounting for ^{17}O containing isotopologues of mass 47 (Table S1). Updating these data to
428 the Brand parameters (section 3.1.2 above) results in a different anchoring of the Soreq data
429 to these Δ_{47} -T lines. The fast drip modern Soreq Cave data in the Gonfiantini parameters has
430 an average Δ_{47} of 0.700‰ (Affek et al., 2014). Using the standard (Z13) calibration resulted
431 in a temperature of 26°C, and using the surface precipitation line (AZ14) resulted in 16°C. As
432 the modern cave temperature varies between 18-19°C when the cave was first opened (in the
433 1970s) to 22°C nowadays, anchoring the calibration to a mid-point between these lines was
434 the reasonable choice. Using the Brand parameters, however, the modern-day fast drip
435 stalagmites have Δ_{47} of 0.693‰. The Z13_{Brand} calibration results in the unlikely temperature
436 of 33°C whereas the AZ14_{Brand} calibration results in 21°C, which is a good fit to the cave
437 temperature in the last few decades. We therefore anchor the Soreq Cave calibration to the
438 surface precipitation experiments using AZ14_{Brand} as a Δ_{47} -T calibration for speleothems, and
439 use that to calculate the paleotemperatures derived from our Δ_{47} data.

440

441 4.1.2. Cave temperatures

442 The main focus in this study is on the two glacial terminations at the transition
443 between the MIS6 to MIS5e (TII) and the LGM to the Holocene (TI). During both TII and
444 TI, characterized by multiple data points, the temperature increased significantly (Fig 5a;
445 Table 1). Through the last glacial, we observe a gradual but variable decrease in temperature
446 from MIS5e towards the LGM, but it is characterized by low resolution data. We therefore
447 discuss the details of the temperature change during the terminations, but only the broad
448 picture during the cooling phase of the last glacial.

449 In both terminations, the peak high temperature of the interglacial coincides in time
450 with a sapropel deposition event that is continuous with the deglaciation warming (S5 and S1
451 in MIS5e and the early Holocene, respectively) (Fig. 5a). Soreq Cave temperatures at the end
452 of MIS6 (157 -142 ka) were 11-14°C and increased to 20°C during S5 in MIS5e (121-128
453 ka), peaking at 22°C at the end of Stage 5e (sample 3-35-D, 120 ka). A distinct temperature
454 low of 15°C occurred during the S5 period at 125 ka (sample SO-15). Overall, a ~10°C rise
455 in temperatures is evident during Termination II to S5 (the TII/S5 period), which include
456 fluctuations from 12°C at 155 ka to 23°C at 139 ka, returning to 11°C at 138ka and warming
457 to 20°C at 128 ka, slight cooling at 125ka and warming to 20-22°C 123-120 ka. These
458 fluctuations in Δ_{47} temperatures match the 3 step increase in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ during the TII/S5 period
459 (labelled i, ii, iii in Fig. 1).

460 Δ_{47} data are compatible with other independent temperature estimates for the 160 ka
461 study period (Fig. 5). The Δ_{47} temperatures compare well with empirical estimates for the
462 Soreq Cave (McGarry et al., 2004) as well as with mean Sea Surface Temperatures (SST)
463 based on alkenone measurements either in sapropel layers and sediments preceding sapropel
464 formation (SST min/max values from several sites in the EMS from Table 3 of Emeis et al.,
465 2003), and in Core 9509 in the Nile Fan (Fig. 1 inset) during the LGM-Holocene transition
466 (Almogi-Labin et al., 2009). All data sets show a similar rise in temperature accompanying
467 the glacial MIS6 to MIS5e transition, cooling during the last glacial period and a similar
468 marked rise in temperatures during the LGM-Holocene transition. The correspondence
469 between Soreq Cave land temperatures and the various SST estimates presented in this
470 section support the interpretation of Bar-Matthews et al. (2003) of a robust sea-land
471 temperature linkage, with similar land and sea surface temperatures during both glacial and
472 interglacial periods.

473 The temperature record presented here for Soreq Cave can be compared with the Δ_{47}
474 temperatures determined by [Rodrigues-Sanz et al. \(2017\)](#) for the 140-115 ka period in core
475 LC21 situated in the EM basin north-east of Crete (Fig.1 inset). The TII temperature rise of
476 $11\pm 4^\circ\text{C}$ in LC21 is similar to that in Soreq. [Rodrigues-Sanz et al. \(2017; their Fig. 3\)](#) also
477 noted a cooling event $4\pm 3^\circ\text{C}$ shortly before Heinrich Stadial 11 (H11- defined at 135-130 ka).
478 The timing of the cooling in both records is not exactly the same; the Soreq cooling to 11°C
479 occurs at 138 ± 4 ka, compared to 135 ka in LC21 samples. However, the age uncertainty in
480 both studies is likely large enough for these dates to overlap, so that it is likely that LC21 and
481 Soreq record the same cooling event. Following this cooling event, LC21 shows warming
482 from 18°C in 135ka to 28°C at 130ka, compared to the warming in Soreq Cave from 11°C at
483 136 ka to 18°C at 131.5 ka. The LC21 temperatures are $28\text{-}26^\circ\text{C}$ during 130-120 ka, whereas
484 the Soreq record shows lower temperatures of $20\text{-}22^\circ\text{C}$, with one notable drop to 15°C at 125
485 ka. Overall, the Δ_{47} temperatures in LC21 are warmer than those in Soreq, but the
486 temperature change in TII is similar. Alkenone U_{37}^k temperatures ([Marino et al., 2007](#))
487 measured in LC21 show an increase from 14 to $\sim 20^\circ\text{C}$ across the 136-130 ka interval and
488 stabilize at $20\text{-}22^\circ\text{C}$ during 127-120 ka. The alkenone temperatures are slightly higher than,
489 but closer to those of the Soreq clumped isotope record.

490 A marked temperature rise is observed during the LGM to Holocene transition (TI).
491 Minimum LGM temperatures are $10\text{-}12^\circ\text{C}$, increasing to $19\text{-}21^\circ\text{C}$ during S1 in the Early
492 Holocene ($\sim 9\text{-}7$ ka). Thus, an approximately 10°C temperature rise is observed also for the
493 TI/S1 period. As was observed in TII/S5, the overall $\sim 10^\circ\text{C}$ increase is not monotonic, but
494 responds to events such as the Bølling Allerød and Younger Dryas (see section 4.4). The
495 temperatures given here by clumped isotopes are comparable with Alkenone U_{37}^k and TEX_{86}
496 SST determined for the last 27 ka ([Castañeda et al., 2010; their Fig. 4](#)) in core GeOB7702-3
497 located on the continental slope, at 562m depth, offshore of central Israel (Fig. 1 inset). The

498 [Castañeda et al. \(2010\)](#) record shows cooling from $\sim 20^{\circ}\text{C}$ to a minimum of 15°C in the 24-19
499 ka period compared to cooling from 18°C to 12°C in the Soreq record at 24-18 ka. The
500 organic proxies then suggest an increase to $\sim 26^{\circ}\text{C}$ (TEX_{86}) and $\sim 24^{\circ}\text{C}$ (alkenones) during the
501 Holocene. These temperatures are somewhat higher than the $19\text{-}21^{\circ}\text{C}$ Δ_{47} temperatures
502 deduced for the Soreq early Holocene-S1 period. The rise in temperatures of $10\text{-}12^{\circ}\text{C}$ during
503 TI suggested by the organic proxies is generally in good agreement with our Δ_{47} temperatures
504 though, if considering that [Castañeda et al. \(2010\)](#) and [Emeis et al. \(2003\)](#) suggest that higher
505 TEX_{86} and U_{37}^k temperatures reflect summer SST associated with *crenarchaeota* and
506 *haphtophyte* blooms in the EM, whereas Soreq Cave reflects mean annual temperatures ([Bar-](#)
507 [Matthews et al., 2003](#)). Nonetheless, there are some differences in the details of the organic
508 proxy temperature rises (mainly TEX_{86}) during TI compared to clumped isotope temperatures
509 that cannot be explained by summer-winter differences.

510 4.1.3. Calcite- water ^{18}O thermometry

511 Temperatures can also be derived from the fluid inclusions $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ data, by combining
512 the water composition with calcite $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{cc}$, using a speleothem specific ^{18}O thermometer
513 calibration ([Tremaine et al., 2011](#)). However, it is immediately clear that a number of the
514 calculated temperatures for the fluid inclusion data are consistently higher than those derived
515 from Δ_{47} , with some values exceeding 30°C (Fig. 6). These anomalous temperatures are
516 primarily found in samples with relatively low water yields, with yields lower than $0.17\ \mu\text{l/g}$
517 defining a point at which erroneous temperatures become evident. When a cut-off of 0.17
518 $\mu\text{l/g}$ between high and low yield samples is applied, the temperatures derived from high
519 water yield samples generally overlap with those derived from Δ_{47} (red circles in Fig. 6 refer
520 to high yield samples, low yield samples are marked as empty circles). This division, based
521 on yield, is supported by the observation of a correlation between the petrography and the
522 distribution of high versus low yield samples. Although low yields may occur in any crystal

523 type, fine-grained samples are more susceptible and within our data set all fine-grained
524 samples resulted in low yield. The commonly observed columnar and fibrous fabrics
525 typically form when speleothems are continuously wet, but where growth occurs slowly at
526 low dissolved carbonate supersaturation (Frisia et al., 2000). Slow crystal growth under
527 continuous water drip in the latter would likely allow more efficient trapping of water in
528 inclusions. The fine grained randomly ordered crystal texture on the other hand is considered
529 to reflect the rapid influx of water that is highly supersaturated with respect to calcium
530 carbonate, thereby allowing rapid nucleation of calcite crystallites (Ayalon et al., 1999;
531 Gonzalez et al., 1992). Such rapid nucleation of calcite crystallites could result in pore space
532 being limited by the competing crystal growth and it is not unreasonable that crystal growth
533 under these conditions would lead to reduced FI yields, as found here for the Soreq samples.

534 The anomalous high temperature values may be linked to the measured FI $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$
535 being erroneously high. This is not because we are at the lower limit of the analytical
536 capabilities *per sé* (standard water injections suggest that lower amounts are measureable),
537 but rather suggest problems related to how well the original fluid inclusion water was
538 quantitatively retained after deposition, or retrieved during analysis. Such effects, resulting in
539 an increase of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ values eventually measured, would lead to apparent temperatures
540 that are too high. Post-depositional alteration of fluid inclusions, either due to oxygen isotope
541 exchange with the surrounding carbonate (Schwarcz et al., 1976) or due to evaporation of
542 inclusions that are not completely sealed (Nehme et al., 2020) cannot be ruled out. However,
543 to increase $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{w,\text{FI}}$ via exchange requires that the exchange occurs at a higher temperature
544 than during deposition, and is therefore unlikely for interglacial sapropel samples.
545 Evaporation of inclusions in Soreq is also unlikely because the continuous presence of water
546 pools in the cave (Bar-Matthews et al., 2003) prevented a large decrease in relative humidity
547 within the cave. Alternatively, diffusive/evaporative water loss from the fluid inclusions

548 within the analytical system, during warming in the crusher (just prior to crushing) could
549 have occurred. Our data do not allow us to determine the exact mechanism, but applying a
550 simple cutoff at $0.17\mu\text{l/g}$ reduces the dataset to temperatures that compare well with the
551 independent Δ_{47} temperatures.

552 FI calcite-water TI temperature variations range from ~ 8 to 22°C and TII
553 temperatures from ~ 10 to 25°C , comparable to the range of Δ_{47} temperatures. Also, the high
554 yield samples through the Last Glacial period give temperatures similar to Δ_{47} . The
555 agreement between high yield samples and Δ_{47} temperatures supports the validity of the fluid
556 inclusion measurements in a semi-arid environment, in samples where sufficiently high water
557 yield is obtained. Moreover, the compatibility between two sets of independent
558 measurements, made in different laboratories and methods, provides strong support for the
559 validity of the methods and calibrations of the thermometers. Due to the possible alteration of
560 the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ signal in the low yield samples they are excluded from further discussion.

561

562

563 4.2. Water oxygen isotope composition

564 The temperature rise during the Terminations will lead to lower oxygen isotope
565 fractionation between cave water and speleothem calcite, and hence contribute to the negative
566 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ peaks in Fig. 1. For example, an overall 10°C rise in temperature from 12 to 22°C
567 would lead to a $\sim 1.9\text{‰}$ decrease in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$. Thus, the temperature changes suggested by Δ_{47}
568 thermometry would only account for part of the overall $\sim 5 - 6\text{‰}$ $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ decrease during TII
569 and TI (Fig. 1). The remaining shift in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ is the result of a decrease in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$.

570 Values of cave drip water $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ are derived in this study by two methods. First, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$
571 (hereafter $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{w,\text{FI}}$) has been measured directly in fluid inclusions (Fig. 2). Here, the *a priori*
572 assumption is that the inclusion water is trapped during the growth of the stalagmite so that

573 these waters are expected to be identical to the cave drip water at the time of calcite
574 formation. However, as noted in the introduction, it has not yet has been fully substantiated if
575 this assumption applies to semi-arid environments such as the EM, and in section 4.1.3 it was
576 shown that the FI $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w,FI}}$ measurements are valid only when sufficiently high water yield is
577 obtained. Second, once temperature has been determined by Δ_{47} , $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ can be derived from
578 the measured $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ using an accepted $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ thermometer calibration (hereafter $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w},\Delta_{47}}$).
579 For this calculation, we use the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ values that were measured in GSI (Table 1) and the
580 calibration of [Tremaine et al. \(2011\)](#), which is specific for speleothems and had been derived
581 from $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ measurements in multiple caves. In this calibration, the fractionation between
582 calcite and water is larger than that in common $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ -T calibrations that are based on
583 laboratory precipitation experiments (e.g., [Kim and O'Neil, 1997](#)), which are mostly
584 consistent with biogenic carbonates. Whereas a larger fractionation has been suggested in
585 some cases to be consistent with water-carbonate isotopic equilibrium in slow mineral growth
586 ([Coplen, 2007](#); [Gabitov et al., 2012](#), [Watkins et al., 2013](#)), in the case of stalagmites it reflects
587 instead the ^{18}O enrichment of the growing calcite due to degassing of CO_2 out of the drip
588 water solution, combined with relatively fast mineral growth (e.g., [Dreybrodt and Scholz,](#)
589 [2011](#); [Affek and Zaarur, 2014](#); [Kluge et al., 2014](#); [Guo and Zhou, 2019](#)). Laboratory
590 speleothem analog experiments in which solution dripped onto a slanted plate and was
591 allowed to flow and form calcite along the plate, resulted in a similar fractionation for the
592 calcite forming close to the drip site, which is analogous to a stalagmite that forms without
593 prior calcite precipitation ([Hansen et al., 2019](#)). Furthermore, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ fractionation was obtained
594 together with the surface precipitation calibration that we use as a speleothem analog
595 calibration for the Δ_{47} thermometer ([Affek and Zaarur, 2014](#)); that fractionation is similar to
596 the [Tremaine et al. \(2011\)](#) multi cave calibration. We therefore consider the latter as the most
597 appropriate $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ calibration to use with our Δ_{47} -derived temperatures to calculate $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w},\Delta_{47}}$.

598 The calculated cave water $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w},\Delta 47}$ vary between -3.5‰ and -8.4‰. The respective
599 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w},\text{FI}}$ varies between -2.5‰ and -7.2‰ (using only the high yield samples), with similar
600 trends in both parameters (Fig. 7). In both these records, the two glacial terminations are
601 characterized by a sharp decrease in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ of 3-4‰. This reflects a decrease in rainfall $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$
602 that is linked to a concomitant change in sea surface $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ due to both global ice melt in
603 deglaciation and the input of ^{18}O -depleted river water during the sapropel events that
604 immediately follow the Terminations. Considering the uncertainty associated with both type
605 of measurement, and the potential slight difference in age between the carbonate pieces used
606 for FI extraction and clumped isotope analysis, we do not expect an exact match between the
607 two measurements so that the general fit indicates good compatibility of the two data sets
608 (Fig. 7). We focus on the Termination periods and their immediate interglacial aftermath
609 (TII/S5 & TI/S1 periods) where water yields are mostly high and both sets of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ data and
610 temperature data generally agree (Figs. 6 and 7).

611

612 4.3. The processes controlling $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ variation: source and amount effects

613 It is clear that a change in water isotopic composition must also contribute to the
614 change in speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$. This leads to the question of what processes control variations
615 in rainfall composition. These may include a number of processes that affect sea surface
616 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$, which is the source of water vapor for the rainfall above the cave, as well as
617 fractionations occurring in atmospheric processes during rainfall formation: (1) A change in
618 the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ of EM seawater as a result of global ice melting, as reflected in changes in relative
619 sea level (RSL), with the incursion of ^{18}O -depleted seawater from the Atlantic to the
620 Mediterranean (Emeis et al., 2003; Kolodny et al, 2005; Grant et al., 2012); (2) riverine input
621 of ^{18}O -depleted freshwater during sapropel events (Emeis et al, 2003); (3) increased Atlantic-
622 sourced rainfall during interglacial periods (Bar-Matthews, 2014); (4) enhanced Rayleigh

623 distillation in times of low sea level, leading to ^{18}O -depletion within the cloud, arising from
624 relatively high cave elevation and distance from the coast (Almogi-Labin et al., 2009;
625 Goldsmith et al., 2017; Grant et al., 2016); (5) variation in the amount of rainfall that are
626 accompanied by changes in rainfall $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ (amount affect; Dansgaard, 1964), suggested to be
627 particularly relevant during interglacial periods (Bar-Matthews et al., 2003); (6) occasional
628 seasonal intrusion of ^{18}O -depleted summer rainfall from monsoon sources (Orland et al.,
629 2012, 2019; Frumkin and Comay 2019; Kiro et al., 2020). These effects may overlap over
630 time, or occur consecutively, and together will contribute to the overall $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ changes in
631 rainfall above the cave, which in turn will be recorded in the speleothems.

632 In order to comprehend the overall cave water $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ shifts during terminations and
633 the ensuing sapropel period, we first estimate the isotopic change in seawater due to
634 processes 1, 2 and 3 using data given by Emeis et al. (2003). The glacial to interglacial RSL
635 rise due to the reduction in ice volume was as much as 100m with an up to 30 km decrease in
636 the distance of the cave from the sea due to landward movement of the coastline. The
637 contribution of ^{18}O -depleted water from ice melt to the EM sea surface water shift during
638 Terminations II and I is estimates as -1.10 and -0.73‰, respectively (Emeis et al., 2003;
639 Table 2 first row).

640 Based on alkenone SST and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$ variations, Emeis et al. (2003) deduced that
641 the overall negative sea surface shifts $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}_{seawater}$ are significantly larger (-2.2‰ in TII/S5
642 and -2.3‰ in T1/S1; Table 2) and combine both ice volume effect during Termination and
643 the river input during sapropel formation. The larger overall negative shifts reflect the
644 additional impact of monsoonal-derived freshwater (low $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$) delivered into the EMS
645 during sapropel events, mainly from the River Nile. Together, these express the potential
646 'source' effect on the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ of rainfall.

647 The corresponding $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ shifts from pre-termination glacial maximum values to
648 peak interglacial (sapropel) values estimated from the combined speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{w,FI}$ and
649 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{w,\Delta 47}$ values (Fig. 7) are -4.4‰ for both T1/S1 and T5/S1 (Table 2 third row). Thus, both
650 glacial to interglacial transition periods are characterized by speleothem $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ decreases
651 that are significantly larger (Residual $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$, Table 2) than those of the corresponding sea
652 surface $\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ deduced by [Emeis et al. \(2003\)](#). Enhanced distillation (4) appears to be an
653 unlikely cause since the glacial Terminations are characterized by sea level rise and coastal
654 retreat, which would favor less distillation (reduced distance and altitude effects) and
655 therefore higher rainfall $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$. Process (6) is viewed as an occasional seasonal intrusion, and
656 would probably not affect the dominance of the EMS surface as the moisture source during
657 interglacial conditions.

658 The remaining process, amount effect (5), expresses the decrease in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ of rainfall
659 with increasing rainfall amount ([Dansgaard, 1964](#)) and was first demonstrated in modern
660 rainfall above Soreq Cave by [Bar-Matthews et al. \(1997\)](#) and [Ayalon et al. \(1998\)](#). Later
661 refinement of the inverse relationship between rainfall amount and rainfall $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ allowed an
662 estimate of rainfall amounts during interglacial events S1 and S5 and interstadial S3 ([Bar-](#)
663 [Matthews et al., 2003](#)). The amount effect reflects dynamic fractionation processes during
664 isotope exchange between cloud vapor and descending rain drops as they pass through the air
665 to the surface. The amount effect occurs in tandem with a temperature-driven effect of ^{18}O
666 enrichment arising from secondary evaporation under the cloud base ([Yang et al., 2019](#) and
667 references cited therein), and only when rainfall density is high does the amount effect mask
668 the temperature effect. These conditions fit the high rainfall amounts proposed by [Bar-](#)
669 [Matthews et al. \(2003\)](#) for warm sapropel periods. Enhanced rainfall during S5 was also a
670 conclusion of the recent study in the Pentadactylos Cave, Kyrenia, Cyprus ([Nehme et al.,](#)
671 [2020](#)) who suggested that the lowest $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values at the onset of and during the MIS5e period

672 were mostly driven by source effects (including S5) and increased rainfall amounts. An
673 analysis of the difference between $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{G.ruber}$ in core LC21 (Grant et al., 2016) and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{cc}$ in
674 Soreq Cave, corrected for sea surface $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ changes, also inferred increased rainfall amounts
675 during the S5 period, but not for the younger sapropels S1-S4 (Grant et al., 2016). The
676 negative residual $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ we calculate here for S1 (Table 2) suggests that enhanced rainfall
677 occurred also during this younger period.

678 As we analyze the overall shift in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$, that includes both the termination and the
679 sapropel event, we cannot partition the relative contributions to the ‘amount effect’ due to
680 each of these climatic events independently. It can be noted though that warm interglacial
681 conditions are expected to favor more positive $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ cave water values, given the present day
682 ~1‰ enrichment of cave water with respect to rainwater (Ayalon et al., 1998). In fact, we
683 observe the opposite, warm sapropel period conditions have the most negative $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ values
684 (Fig. 7). The amount effect is clearly a powerful influence during these time periods. Further
685 insight into the relative timing of the temperature and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ changes is given in the following
686 section.

687

688 4.4. The relative timing of temperature and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ shifts

689 The previous sections showed that both temperature increase and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ decrease
690 contribute to the overall shift in speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{cc}$ in both glacial-interglacial transitions. A
691 critical question arising from these data is the relative timing of temperature increase and
692 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ decrease during the glacial-interglacial changes. Here we address the relative timing
693 and connections between $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{cc}$, temperature, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$, and RSL. The overall timing of events
694 is summarized as age versus $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{cc}$, T, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$, d-excess and RSL plots (Fig. 8), with more
695 detailed plots of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{cc}$, cc-water T (temperatures derived from $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{cc}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{w,FI}$), Δ_{47} T

696 and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ focusing on changes during glacial-interglacial transitions during the Late Glacial
697 MIS6- MIS5e/S5 transition (Fig 9a-d) and LGM to present (Fig 9e-h). The discussion is
698 subdivided into consecutive time periods:

699 1. *The Late Glacial MIS6-MIS5e/S5 transition*

700 This transition includes samples from 155 ± 2 ka to 120 ± 2 ka (Table 1). Overall three
701 distinct steps in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{cc}$ are identified during this transition (Figs.1, 9a). During the earlier part
702 of this period (Late Glacial MIS6-early Termination II pre-H11 temperature high at 139 ± 3 ka
703 (Table 1)), $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{cc}$ decreases (step i Fig. 9a) and temperatures derived either from FI or Δ_{47}
704 decrease (Figs. 9b,c) whereas $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ values are approximately constant at $\sim -4\text{‰}$ (Fig. 9d).
705 RSL at this period is low, and rises only slightly toward the end of the time interval (Fig. 8e),
706 which suggests that parameters such as sea surface composition and rainfall distillation due to
707 distance/altitude effect did not change significantly, consistent with the constant cave water
708 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$. It is thus evident that step i in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{cc}$ record is due to an early increase in
709 temperature that occurs prior to changes in sea water isotopic composition or hydrological
710 conditions.

711 The mid-Termination II–MIS5e/S5 period (138 ± 4 ka to 120 ± 2 ka) encompasses the
712 second and third steps of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{cc}$ decrease: step (ii) during the glacial termination is a $\sim 1\text{‰}$
713 shift and step iii is a $\sim 3\text{‰}$ shift (Fig. 9a). The temperature rise in step ii is from 11 to 18°C
714 (Fig 9c); $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{w,FI}$ values for high yield samples (closed red circles) decrease from ~ -4.5 to -7
715 ‰ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{w,\Delta_{47}}$ values from -4.5 to -5.5‰ (Fig 9d). Δ_{47} Temperatures are $20\text{--}22^\circ\text{C}$ during
716 step (iii), with the exception of the notable drop to 15°C at 125 ka, (Fig. 9c), and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$
717 values further decrease to -8.4‰ , before rising to -4.5‰ at the end of S5 (120 ka). It follows
718 that both temperature rise and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ decrease contribute to steps ii and iii $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{cc}$ decrease.
719 However, the data resolution is not sufficient to pinpoint the exact relative timing of the
720 temperature and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ contributions to each step.

721 2. *Last Glacial Period (115-20 ka)*. During this period a general cooling from 20 to
722 ~10°C and a rise in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ are observed, while $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ values increase slightly but
723 systematically (Fig. 8c). $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ values are highest at the LGM. The last glacial period is
724 characterized by a progressive increase in global ice volume that leads to a decrease in RSL
725 (Fig. 8e) and drives sea surface $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ to more positive values. On the other hand, greater
726 rainfall distillation owing to the increased distance from the coast (and altitude) due to the
727 lower sea level would have the opposite effect, lowering rainfall $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$. It thus appears that
728 these two opposing driving forces for rainfall $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ partially compensate each other
729 throughout the Last glacial period, resulting in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ that fluctuates and increases only from
730 ~-5‰ to -3‰.

731 3. *LGM to present (25-0 ka)*. This period covers the Termination I-Sapropel S1
732 (TI/S1) period. Though less clearly shown than in TII, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ changes can also be viewed in
733 terms of three steps, labelled here *i*, *ii* and *iii* (Fig. 9e). These include step *i* at the end of the
734 Last Glacial (25-20 ka) in which $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ rises by ~1.5 ‰ and Δ_{47} derived temperatures fall by
735 ~6°C. Step *ii* (20-12 ka) is Termination 1 and shows an overall 4 ‰ $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ decrease and
736 10°C temperature increase (10-20°C) derived either from FI or Δ_{47} (Figs. 9f, g). This period
737 includes the Bølling-Allerød and the Younger Dryas. Contrary to the expected warm BA and
738 cold YD, Δ_{47} suggests the opposite temperature trend (Fig. 9g). However, the age uncertainty
739 in these samples does not allow to reliably identify the BA and YD events in the Δ_{47} data.
740 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ in step *ii* is approximately constant, suggesting that as in TII also here the temperature
741 increase dominates any hydrological changes as the driving force for the changes in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$.
742 During this time, the reduction in global ice volume results in ^{18}O -depletion of Mediterranean
743 Sea water. The observation that $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ in the cave does not decrease too, likely indicates
744 reduced distillation, related to the increase in RSL (Fig. 8e).

745 Step iii is the time of S1. The temperature reached its maximum so that the additional
746 decrease in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ is due to a decrease in cave water $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ (Figs. 9g, h). This depletion
747 reflects the combination of the EMS depletion due to input of low $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ waters together with
748 a larger amount of rainfall. It thus seems that the effect of rainfall amounts begins relatively
749 late, when warm conditions were already well established during S1.

750

751 4.5. Climatic significance of d-excess variations

752 The primary control on d-excess is kinetic fractionation of oxygen and hydrogen
753 isotopes in the diffusive transport of water vapor from the sea surface to the free troposphere
754 (Craig and Gordon, 1963; Merlivat and Jouzel, 1979; Gat, 1996). This kinetic fractionation is
755 strongly dependent on the relative humidity (RH) gradient above the sea surface, which is the
756 difference in moisture content between 100% RH at the sea surface and the lower RH in
757 upper air. The lower the RH in the air the greater will be the kinetic fractionation effect,
758 leading to higher d-excess values. On a global scale this humidity gradient is expressed by
759 the GMWL equation with d-excess of 10‰, corresponding to a mean RH ~80% at an
760 evaporation temperature of ~26°C (Dansgaard, 1964; Merlivat and Jouzel, 1979). However,
761 local variations are frequent due to regional factors in the rainfall system. As noted in section
762 3.2, in present-day the rainfall in the EM region occurs mostly during the winter months
763 (December to February) when cold and dry air moving from the European land mass passes
764 over the warm EMS. Enhanced evaporation from the warm EMS into the dry atmospheric
765 wind system is characterized by an unusually high RH gradient, leading to d-excess values
766 greater than 20‰ (Ziv et al., 2006). The high EMMWL d-excess generated at the sea surface
767 may be further modified by cloud processes. Evaporation of water droplets below the cloud
768 base would result in lower d-excess values relative to those generated above the sea (Gat,
769 1996). d-excess values similar to the present day EMMWL were suggested to be

770 characteristic of past interglacials ([Matthews et al., 2000](#); [McGarry et al., 2004](#)) based on FI
771 δD measurements and estimated $\delta^{18}O_w$ values.

772 The d-excess values of Soreq Cave water are calculated using the measured δD_{FI}
773 values and either $\delta^{18}O_{w,FI}$ (using only the high yield samples) or $\delta^{18}O_{w,\Delta 47}$ values (Fig. 8d).
774 Both sets of data are comparable during pre-termination late glacial periods, during the
775 terminations themselves, and during the ensuing warm periods. Thus, d-excess values similar
776 to the present day EMMWL (>22‰) are evident in warm periods in the past (Holocene,
777 MIS5e/S5), whereas lower d-excess values, similar to the GMWL, occur in colder periods
778 (LGM, early MIS3 (60-50 ka), MIS5a/4 (80-70 ka), Late MIS6/early TII). Transitions from
779 GMWL to EMMWL d-excess values occur during the LGM to Holocene transition, between
780 70 and 60 ka, and during the transition from MIS6/Early TII to MIS5e; the converse d-excess
781 decrease occurs between 80 and 70 ka and after MIS5e (Fig. 8d). These fluctuations in d-
782 excess generally match sharp rise and fall in RSL (Fig 8e). It thus appears d-excess is low
783 during cold periods with low RSL. Several different scenarios can explain these d-excess
784 variations. Three main possibilities are detailed as follows:

- 785 • [Nehme et al. \(2020\)](#) inferred that speleothem $\delta^{18}O_{w,FI}$ and $\delta D_{w,FI}$ data from MIS6 to MIS5
786 in the Pentadactylos cave in northern Cyprus follows an evaporation line. They
787 interpreted this trend to reflect water evaporation within the fluid inclusions during or
788 after the formation of the inclusion, at times when the relative humidity in the cave is
789 low. However, such evaporation is unlikely in the continuously high RH conditions of the
790 Soreq Cave.
- 791 • A second scenario would involve higher relative humidity above the Mediterranean Sea
792 during cold periods. [Goldsmith et al. \(2017\)](#) examined this possibility and suggested two
793 possible scenarios for the GMWL-type d-excess: 1) Both the normalized humidity
794 (atmospheric vapor pressure relative to saturated vapor pressure at SST) over the EMS

795 and the cloud-rain Rayleigh distillation were 10-20% higher than today, reflecting greater
796 rainout, or 2) Rayleigh distillation was similar to today, but normalized humidity was
797 10% lower. [Goldsmith et al. \(2017\)](#) favored the first scenario, arguing that the ice covered
798 European continent during the LGM would favor high pressure systems that drove air
799 streams of Atlantic origin along the length of the Mediterranean Sea. Such air streams
800 could generate air masses with higher normalized humidity relative to today, i.e., glacial
801 Atlantic air, which is more humid than glacial Mediterranean air, picks up moisture in the
802 EMS under smaller relative humidity gradient conditions. This model agrees with
803 previous studies ([Florineth and Schlüchter, 2000](#); [McGarry et al., 2004](#)) suggesting that
804 Atlantic vapor transport shifted southward over southern Europe, allowing air masses
805 with higher humidity to develop over the Mediterranean.

806 • A third scenario is that the lower glacial d-excess values reflect lower temperatures.
807 [McGarry et al. \(2004\)](#), based on [Gat \(1996\)](#), showed that significant lowering of sea
808 surface temperatures would produce lower d-excess values due to the larger ratio of the
809 equilibrium fractionation factors between ^{18}O and D during equilibrium evaporation
810 above the sea (the slope of the MWL). Most interestingly, modelling of physiographic
811 controls of climates conditions of the EM region during the late glacial pre-LGM times
812 (30-25 ka) ([Enzel et al., 2008](#)) suggests that Cyprus low cyclones were primarily funneled
813 into this region rather than further to the north as they do today. As these are similar
814 systems to those bringing rain to the cave region nowadays, relative humidity in the
815 sources might not have been markedly different from today, but temperatures were
816 certainly lower.

817 It is likely that both storm tracks involving moist Atlantic air streams along the
818 Mediterranean Sea and enhanced funneling of Cyprus low cyclones over the lower
819 temperature EM sea could have contributed to the low d-excess values during glacial

820 conditions. However, more detailed and high resolution studies are required to resolve the
821 exact mechanisms controlling the d-excess shifts.

822

823 5. Conclusions

824 New carbonate clumped isotope and fluid inclusion δD_w and $\delta^{18}O_w$ data have allowed
825 us to partition the temperature and water composition components of the Soreq Cave $\delta^{18}O_{cc}$
826 record of the last 160 ka. Peak interglacial temperatures in the Holocene and MIS5e were 20-
827 22°C, whereas minimum glacial temperatures, in the LGM and late MIS6 are 11-12°C. The
828 resulting $\sim 10^\circ\text{C}$ warming through glacial terminations is comparable to the estimated SST
829 warming from either organic proxies or foraminiferal clumped isotopes in the EMS. At the
830 same time, significant decreases in $\delta^{18}O_w$ are observed both in the termination itself and in
831 the following EMS sapropel events. This ^{18}O -depletion is partially, but not fully, accounted
832 for by a decrease in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of Mediterranean Sea water that is the moisture source for rainfall
833 in Soreq vicinity. About half of the shift in $\delta^{18}O_w$ must come from the rain system dynamics,
834 associated with enhanced Rayleigh distillation and amount of rainfall. The initial step of the
835 glacial termination is characterized by warming only, with no significant change in $\delta^{18}O_w$,
836 suggesting that the depletion of sea water is approximately balanced by a reduced rainfall
837 distillation, possibly due to the sea level rise and resulting shorter distance from the coast to
838 Soreq Cave.

839 Fluid inclusions data allowed a direct calculation of d-excess in cave water, indicating
840 low d-excess, similar to the GMWL, in cold time periods, and high d-excess, similar to
841 modern-day EMMWL, characteristic of warm interglacials. This shift may reflect a change in
842 storm tracks so that glacial relative humidity over the Mediterranean has been higher than

843 today, or lower glacial temperatures affecting the isotope fractionation during sea surface
844 evaporation leading to a higher $\delta\text{D}-\delta^{18}\text{O}$ slope and hence to lower d-excess.

845

846 **CRedit Author Statement**

847 **A Matthews (equal first author):** Conceptualization; investigation; formal analysis;
848 writing—original draft; visualization. **HJ Affek (equal first author):** Conceptualization;
849 validation; methodology; investigation; formal analysis; writing—original first draft. **A.**
850 **Ayalon:** Conceptualization; methodology; investigation; resources; writing—original draft.
851 **H.B Vonhof:** Resources; methodology; writing –original draft. **M. Bar-Matthews:**
852 Conceptualization; investigation; project administration; writing—original draft.

853 **Declaration of Competing Interest.**

854 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
855 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this study.

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863

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 1184 **Figure 1:** $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ profile of Soreq Cave for the last 185 ka (Bar-Matthews et al., 2019).
 1185 Boundaries between major marine isotope stages (MIS) are indicated by the grey vertical lines.
 1186 These boundaries are: 6/5 130 ka; 5/4 71 ka, 4/3 60 ka; 3/2 25ka; 2/1 11 ka. (Martinson et al.,
 1187 1987; Grant et al., 2012). The approximate timing of sapropel events are shown by S
 1188 numbering. The controversial ‘missing’ S2 sapropel event (Cita et al., 1977) is indicated as S2?
 1189 and its equivalent timing is based on low $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ event II defined in Bar-Matthews et al. (2000).
 1190 The two Terminations I and II are marked by TI and TII, respectively. The noted stepwise
 1191 increases in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ during the late glacial MIS6 to MIS5e transition are indicated by the
 1192 numerals i, ii, and iii, respectively. Isotopically, Sapropel events correspond to negative peaks
 1193 in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$ record, whereas cold dry glacial periods are characterized by the highest $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$
 1194 values. Inset figure shows location of Soreq Cave and EMS cores specifically referred to in
 1195 this work.
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Figure 2. Δ_{47} versus age plot showing the variation of Δ_{47} values (given in the absolute reference frame, using the Brand parameters) with time. Error bars follow Table 1. Sapropel periods are shown by grey bars and their timing is based on: Grant et al. (2012): S5; de Lange et al. (2008): S1; Grant et al. (2016): S3 and S4; Bar-Matthews et al. (2000): S2?. Vertical lines indicate the boundaries between major MIS events. S (gray) and T (green) numbering and shading refer to the timing of EM sapropel periods and glacial Terminations, respectively.

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 1207 **Figure 3.** $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ (a) and δD_w (b) versus age for fluid inclusions. Errors on age and isotope
 1208 values follow Table 1. Time period markers are as in Fig. 2.
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Figure 4. δD_w versus $\delta^{18}O_w$ in fluid inclusion data from this study. The data symbols refer to the marine isotope stage that the samples belong to. The suffixes YD, BA and LGM refer to the Younger Dryas, Bølling-Allerød, and Last Glacial Maximum, respectively. The line labelled GMWL represents the global meteoric water line ($\delta D=8*\delta^{18}O+10$) and the line labelled EMMWL represents the Eastern Mediterranean meteoric water line (Gat and Carmi 1987: $\delta D=8*\delta^{18}O+22$). The grey shaded area represents δD_w versus $\delta^{18}O_w$ range of modern rainfall above the Soreq Cave, which plots around the EMMWL (Ayalon et al., 2004). Research on the modern Soreq Cave water shows that although they are ~1‰ more enriched in $\delta^{18}O_w$ and ~ 10‰ in δD_w relative to the concomitant rainfall, they still plot along the EMMWL (Bar-Matthews et al., 1996; Ayalon et al., 1998). This offset reflects mixing in the soil zone between ^{18}O and D-depleted rainfall during the middle of the rainy season and more enriched rainfall at the beginning and the end of the rainy season (Ayalon et al., 1998; Orland et al., 2009; Orland et al., 2012). Cave water values thus provide a good proxy for regional rainfall above the Soreq Cave.

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 1228 **Figure 5.** Temperature versus age. (a) Plot of Δ_{47} temperatures versus mean sample age (as
 1229 given in Table 1). Δ_{47} temperatures are determined using the AZ14_{Brand} calibration (as given
 1230 in the text). (b) Comparison of Soreq Cave Δ_{47} temperatures with empirical Soreq Cave
 1231 temperature estimates based on fluid inclusion δD systematics (McGarry et al., 2004) and
 1232 alkenone-based sea surface temperatures (SST; Emeis et al., 2003 and Almogi-Labin et al.,

1233 2009). Alkenone SST data for the 'missing sapropel' period are taken from Emeis et al.,
1234 (1998). Legend: Blue circles = Δ_{47} temperatures; green diamonds =Temperatures according
1235 to McGarry et al. (2004); red diamonds = SST data of Emeis et al. (1998, 2003); orange
1236 diamonds = SST data of Almogi-Labin et al. (2009).
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Figure 6. Temperatures derived from calcite-FI water ^{18}O thermometry plotted as a function of age and compared to the respective temperatures derived from Δ_{47} (blue circles). Closed red circles refer to high yield samples; open black circles refer to low yield samples.

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Figure 7. $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ versus age, comparing values measured in fluid inclusions ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{w,FI}$) with values calculated based on Δ_{47} temperatures and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{cc}$ data ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{w,\Delta 47}$) using the calcite-water fractionation equation of [Tremaine et al. \(2011\)](#). Errors in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{w,\Delta 47}$ are propagated from the error range of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{cc}$ values ($\pm 0.5\text{‰}$) and the Δ_{47} temperature errors given in Table 1. The grey vertical bars indicate the duration of the sapropel periods.

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Figure 8. Five stacked age plots comparing the overall (160 ka) timing of major variations in (a) $\delta^{18}O_{cc}$, (b) Δ_{47} temperatures, (c) $\delta^{18}O_w$ values, (d) d-excess and (e) probabilistic relative sea level (RSL; Grant et al., 2012). Zones i, iii, iii in (a) indicate the three steps of increase in $\delta^{18}O_{cc}$ observed in Soreq Cave during TII, as noted in Fig. 1.

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Figure 9. High resolution plots for glacial-interglacial transitions. Plots showing (a) $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$, (b) calcite- $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w,FI}}$ temperatures (cc-water T), (c) Δ_{47} temperatures and (d) $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ values versus age for 160-110 ka cover the late glacial MIS6, Termination II, and the MIS5e/S5 period. Plots showing (e) $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{cc}}$, (f) calcite- $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w,FI}}$ temperatures (cc-water T), (g) Δ_{47} temperatures and (h) $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ values versus age $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ profiles for 25 ka-present cover the LGM, Termination I, and Holocene/S1

Table 1 Primary data

Sample ID	Mean Age ka	Age Error ka	$\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{Occ}}$ ‰ PDB GSI	$\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{Occ}}$ ‰ SMOW GSI	FI Yield $\mu\text{l/g}$	δD FI ‰ SMOW	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ FI ‰ SMOW	d-excess FI ‰ SMOW	T°C (^{18}O) GSI-FI	Δ_{47} ‰ Brand	Error Δ_{47} 1SE	T°C, AZ14, Brand	T error 1SE	$\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{w}}$ (Δ_{47}) ‰ SMOW	d-excess (Δ_{47}) ‰ SMOW
SOREQ CAVE															
Modern Average															
2.20 A	0.50	0.30	-5.00	25.76	0.04	nm	nm	nm		0.693		21.0			
SO-38	0.10	0.10	-5.00	25.76	0.44	-8.06	-5.39	35.1	17.4	0.673	0.003	27.2	1.0	-3.59	20.7
5-3 best:	0.03		-5.00	25.76	nm	nm	nm	nm		0.675	0.002	26.6	0.7	-3.70	
Pool 2a,	0.55	0.15	-5.30	25.45	0.00	nm	nm	nm		0.680	0.002	25.0	0.6	-4.29	
2-6-A-1*	1.15	0.25	-5.25	25.50	0.09	-20.76	-4.43	14.7	23.9	0.699	0.005	19.0	1.5	-5.35	22.1
11-24B(1)	5.50	0.20	-5.50	25.24	0.48	-21.48	-4.94	18.0	22.5	0.715	0.014	14.2	4.0	-6.51	30.6
11-24B(2)	5.50	0.20	-5.50	25.24	0.68	-19.16	-6.60	33.6	13.7	0.715	0.014	14.2	4.0	-6.51	32.9
11-24 E	5.80		-5.80	24.93	nm	nm	nm	nm		0.698	0.003	19.2	0.9	-5.86	
11-24J	6.45	0.15	-5.70	25.03	0.02	nm	nm	nm		0.704	0.006	17.4	1.8	-6.09	
11-24K	6.80		-6.10	24.62	nm	nm	nm	nm		0.710	0.013	15.7	3.8	-6.81	
2-8 E*	8.45	0.85	-6.50	24.21	0.04	nm	nm	nm		0.696	0.002	19.9	0.6	-6.43	
2-20(1-5)*	8.00	0.80	-6.11	24.61	0.10	-19.65	-5.37	23.3	23.5	0.702	0.001	18.0	0.3	-6.39	31.4
10--44(50-60)A	12.35	0.65	-4.64	26.13	0.13	0.77	-3.07	25.3	28.1	0.692	0.004	21.0	1.2	-4.36	35.7
10--44(1-10)	14.75	0.75	-3.73	27.06	0.10	-8.04	-4.20	25.6	17.0	0.693	0.003	20.7	0.9	-3.51	20.0
10--44(10-20)	16.10	0.90	-3.27	27.54	0.36	-23.71	-4.07	8.9	15.3	0.702	0.003	18.1	0.9	-3.54	4.6
10--44(20-30)	16.65	1.15	-3.52	27.28	0.41	-25.77	-4.24	8.1	15.7	0.723	0.017	11.8	4.7	-5.00	14.2
12-Z-b (2)*	19.00	0.20	-2.50	28.33	0.26	-16.66	-2.45	3.0	19.8	0.724	0.002	11.6	0.6	-4.03	15.5
7-23 1 st *	20.30	0.50	-2.50	28.33	0.19	-21.76	-4.73	16.1	8.1	0.729	0.006	10.2	1.7	-4.31	12.7
7-23 2 nd *	20.30	0.50	-2.50	28.33	0.27	-18.90	-3.47	8.8	14.5	0.729	0.006	10.2	1.7	-4.31	15.5
10-41(265-285)	25.00	3.00	-3.20	27.61	0.03	nm	nm	nm		0.701	0.016	18.3	4.7	-3.43	
1-4P (150-185)	34.80	0.50	-2.80	28.02	0.15	-12.52	-4.22	21.3	12.1	0.722	0.009	12.1	2.5	-4.22	21.3
2-21-I	45.00	1.00	-3.10	27.71	0.16	5.81	-1.24	15.8	29.7	0.711	0.004	15.3	1.2	-3.89	36.9
9-25A	49.80	0.80	-3.60	27.20	0.49	-20.84	-3.85	10.0	18.1	0.700	0.006	18.6	1.8	-3.77	9.3
9-25G*	55.70	0.10	-3.95	26.84	0.35	-27.88	-4.94	11.6	14.3	0.708	0.006	16.2	1.8	-4.57	8.7
3-22A2	60.00	0.70	-4.10	26.68	0.12	-6.89	-3.97	24.9	20.2	0.726	0.007	10.9	2.0	-5.75	39.1
11-27A	67.60	1.10	-3.40	27.40	0.14	-5.75	-2.86	17.1	22.4	0.699	0.013	18.8	3.9	-3.53	22.5
11-27C-E	69.70	1.80	-3.45	27.35	0.17	-35.99	-4.58	0.6	13.6	0.705	0.010	17.1	3.0	-3.90	-4.8
11-27F	76.00	2.00	-4.50	26.27	0.19	-29.42	-3.94	2.1	22.5	0.695	0.005	20.1	1.5	-4.39	5.7
11-27h-k	80.50	1.80	-4.10	26.68	0.32	-9.65	-2.49	10.2	28.4	0.709	0.009	15.9	2.6	-4.78	28.6
11.27O,P	86.00	2.00	-5.20	25.55	0.03	nm	nm	nm		0.697	0.004	19.5	1.2	-5.20	
11-27 U,V	103.70	1.50	-5.00	25.76	0.08	-16.73	-4.68	20.7	21.3	0.713	0.010	14.9	2.9	-5.88	30.3
3-35B	114.00	3.00	-4.66	26.11	0.10	-6.80	-2.68	14.7	30.4						-6.8
4-20A	114.50	5.50	-4.90	25.86	0.14	-12.52	-3.13	12.5	29.3	0.705	0.007	17.0	2.1	-5.37	30.4
3.35D	120.00	2.00	-5.10	25.65	0.04	nm	nm	nm		0.690	0.009	21.8	2.8	-4.67	
SO-15A	123.00	1.50	-7.59	23.09	0.16	-14.08	-4.42	-21.3	37.5	0.695	0.002	20.3	0.6	-7.44	
SO-15A(2)	123.00	1.50	-7.59	23.09	0.15	-16.97	-5.78	29.2	29.6	0.695	0.002	20.3	0.6	-7.44	42.5
SO-15	125.00	1.50	-7.59	23.09	0.06	-34.83	nm	nm		0.711	0.007	15.4	2.0	-8.36	
SO-15B(2)	127.50	1.00	-7.59	23.09	0.26	-29.31	-6.45	22.3	25.8	0.695	0.012	20.3	3.7	-7.44	30.2
2-22 A1,A2	131.95	2.25	-5.25	25.50	0.22	-23.46	-7.23	34.4	9.3	0.703	0.012	17.8	3.6	-5.58	21.2
2-22 A3 (1)	136.00	2.00	-4.75	26.01	0.31	-27.75	-4.64	9.4	20.1	0.706	0.010	16.8	2.9	-5.27	14.4
2-22 A3-A4	138.00	4.00	-4.75	26.01	0.52	-22.83	-5.42	20.6	16.0	0.726	0.006	11.1	1.7	-6.36	28.1
2-22 A3-A4(2)	138.00	4.00	-4.75	26.01	0.38	-27.52	-4.95	12.1	18.4	0.726	0.006	11.1	1.7	-6.36	23.4
2-22 A4	139.25	3.25	-4.75	26.01	0.47	-25.70	-4.43	9.8	21.2	0.687	0.006	22.8	1.9	-4.14	7.4
2-22 B(2)	144.10	2.10	-3.50	27.30	0.21	-21.46	-4.74	16.5	13.0	0.715	0.009	14.1	2.6	-4.54	14.8
2-22 C3	155.00	2.0	-3.20	27.61	0.46	-23.32	-3.92	8.0	15.7	0.724	0.012	11.5	3.3	-4.74	14.6

* samples with Δ_{47} recalculated from Affek et al (2008)

1263 **Table 2.** Contributions to overall $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ variations during glacial-interglacial changes at
 1264 Termination I & Sapropel S1 (TI/S1) and Termination II & Sapropel S5 (TII/S5)

	$\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ ‰	$\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ ‰
	TI/S1	TII/S5
Ice volume effect during Terminations	-0.73	-1.10
Overall seawater (ice volume effect+ Sapropel riverine input)	-2.3	-2.2
Speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$ shifts (this study)	-4.4	-4.4
Residual $\delta^{18}\text{O}_w$	-2.3	-2.2

1265 *Data for samples S5/ODP967 and S1/ODP969 in Table 4b (Emeis et al., 2003)

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Declaration of Competing Interest.

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this study.

CRedit Author Statement

A Matthews (equal first author): Conceptualization; investigation; formal analysis; writing–original draft; visualization. **HJ Affek (equal first author):** Conceptualization; validation; methodology; investigation; formal analysis; writing–original first draft. **A. Ayalon:** Conceptualization; methodology; investigation; resources; writing–original draft. **H.B Vonhof:** Resources; methodology; writing –original draft. **M. Bar-Matthews:** Conceptualization; investigation; project administration; writing–original draft.